

BOSHLANG'ICH TA'LIM JARAYONIDA TOLERANTLIKNI TARBIYALASH USULLARI VA VOSITALARI

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Gafurova Nodira Ravshanovna

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Bag'rikenglikni insonning boshqa odamlarga bo'lgan munosabatining ko'rinishlaridan biri sifatida anglash, tarbiya bu munosabatni salbiy bo'lsa ham o'zgartirmasligi mumkin: biz bolani o'z qarashlarini o'zgartirishga, fikrlashga majburlashga bizda haqqimiz yo'q. Gap shundaki, u ilgari tanimagan narsani tan olishi, ilgari sevmagan narsasini sevib qolishini tan olishi mumkin. U o'z munosabatiga ega. Bunda gap boshqacha va murakkabroq - bag'rikenglik o'z sub'ekti va ob'ektini birgalikda yashash holati bilan ta'minlashi mumkin va kerak; bag'rikenglik tarbiyasi bolaga ushbu vaziyatga adekvat yordam berish uchun mo'ljallangan.

Tolerantlikning asosi va uning dinamikasining mumkin bo'lgan maydoni, yuqorida aytib o'tilganidek, birinchi navbatda, shaxsning tajribasida yotadi va ishlaydi. Demak, bag'rikenglik tarbiyasi - bu pedagogik nuqtai nazardan, bag'rikenglikning ijobiy tajribasini maqsadli tashkil etish, ya'ni boshqalarning nazarida ular qanday bo'lishidan qat'i nazar, ular bilan o'zaro munosabatni talab qiladigan shart-sharoitlarni maqsadli ravishda yaratishdir.

Tolerantlik tajribasi, ijobiy (yaratilgan normal munosabatlar) yoki salbiy (munosabatning salbiyligi) har bir odamga, shu jumladan "sevimli" va "sevmagan" odamlarga ega bo'lgan eng kichik bolada ham mavjud. Bundan tashqari, maktab o'quvchilari har xil xarakterga, temperamentlarga, g'oyalarga, umidlarga, xatti-harakatlarga ega bo'lgan, lekin maktab qoidalarini, sinf o'qituvchisini, u yoki bu o'qituvchini, sinfdagi kimnidir qabul qilishga (yoki hatto toqat qilishga) majbur bo'lgan bunday tajribaga ega.

Yana bir narsa ham prinsipial ahamiyatga ega: bag'rikenglikni tarbiyalash jarayoni o'zaro bo'lsa samaraliroq bo'ladi. Albatta, bunday vaziyatni yaratish juda qiyin, ammo bu "aloqa" sharoitida mumkin. Va shu bilan birga, bag'rikenglik tajribasi o'zaro boyib boradi, bu hissiy, intellektual va axloqiy maydonni yaratadi, buni asosida munosabatlar va muloqotning ijobiy tajribasi o'sadi. Bunday sohaning mavjudligi yoki yaratilishi ustozning jiddiy omadidir!

Bolalar hayotini tashkil qilishda individual bolaning ham, jamoaning ham (guruh, jamoa) bag'rikengligini rag'batlantiradigan vaziyatlar yaratiladi, ya'ni bag'rikenglikni keltirib chiqaradigan, unga bo'lgan ehtiyojni yo'qotadigan turmush tarzi yaratiladi.

Samarali pedagogik vositalar bola yoki guruhning o'z tajribasida paydo bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan (boshqa odamlar tajribasidan ma'lum) va aks ettirish haqidagi ma'lumot bo'lishi mumkin.

Tegishli ma'lumotlarning manbalari - folklor yoki adabiy qahramonlar va haqiqiy odamlar, ko'pincha butunlay boshqacha odamlarning paydo bo'ladigan munosabatlari, hushyorlik, ishonchsizlik, hatto dushmanlikdan tortib o'zaro qabul qilishgacha. Bu yerda ham bolaning yoki jamiyatning o'z tajribasi qimmatli, ayniqsa, taniqli va shuning uchun ishonchli, qiyin vaziyatlarni ijobiy hal qilish kabi misollarni keltirishimiz mumkin.

Ikkinchisi bilan bog'liq holda, biz o'qituvchi tomonidan tashkil etilgan bunday qarorlarning aksini ta'kidlaymiz. Bu aksiologik va axloqiy jihatdan ahamiyatli chegaralarda tolerantlikning keyingi namoyon bo'lishi uchun muhim asos bo'lgan ijobiy tajribani birgalikda tajribali baholash sifatida ulkan ta'lim salohiyatiga ega.

Taklif etilayotgan o'quv-uslubiy qo'llanmada Farg'ona, Andijon, Namangan va Toshkent shaharlaridagi boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'quv jarayoniga tatbiq etilgan bag'rikenglik madaniyatini tarbiyalash bo'yicha sinfdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish tajribasi jamlangan. Dasturiy ta'minot usulining asosi Ijtimoiy-pedagogik shart-sharoitlarni shakllantirish va bag'rikenglik madaniyatini tarbiyalash bo'yicha pedagogik faoliyatni ta'limni qo'llab-quvvatlash dasturi "Bag'rikenglik madaniyatini tarbiyalash" Biz boshqachamiz - biz do'stmiz " mavzularida o'z aksini topgan.

Bag'rikenglikka yo'naltirilgan ta'limda tarbiya funktsiyasi bolalar va kattalar o'rtasidagi maqsadli o'zaro ta'sir sifatida namoyon bo'ladi, bola va uning atrofidagi dunyo sub'ektlari o'rtasida qiymat-semantik bag'rikenglik muloqotini shakllantirishga hissa qo'shadi, uning o'ziga xos usulini (atrof-muhitini) shakllantiradi. Bolaning hayoti va uning o'zini o'zi belgilash, ijodkorlik va ijodiy hayot tajribasini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishga hissa qo'shishga xizmat qiladi.

Shunday qilib, bola to'liq huquqli sub'ekt bo'lgan ta'lim faoliyati jarayonida kattalar va bola o'rtasidagi muloqotning roli kuchayadi.

Bola rivojlanishining turli bosqichlarida ta'limning uzluksizligi masalasi alohida ahamiyatga ega. Uning shaxsini shakllantirish qonuniyatlarini tushunish, ta'lim faoliyatiga o'ziga xos yondashuvlarni bilish zamonaviy o'qituvchining eng

muhim vazifasidir.

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